

Was Interbreeding between Neanderthals and modern humans strongly sex biased?

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When Green et al. demonstrated that non-African humans carry Neanderthal alleles (1), the question of whether the matings that gave rise to this mixing were sexually symmetric went unanswered. Platt et al. make an imaginative attempt to address it: the proposition that sex-biased mating would leave a predictable asymmetry in X-linked versus autosomal ancestry patterns is a genuinely elegant approach to recovering behavioral information from ancient genomes, and the question itself is among the most evocative in paleoanthropology. However, the reported X:autosome signals do not sufficiently exclude a neutral drift null under symmetric mating.

Platt et al. interpret excess anatomically modern human (AMH) alleles on the Neanderthal X chromosomes and the depletion of Neanderthal alleles on AMH X as evidence that interbreeding was predominantly between male Neanderthals and female AMHs. The issue is that the reported statistic is not an explicit detection of mate direction frequencies. The pattern is compatible with asymmetric mating, but also with drift.

My argument is based on a much simpler null. Under symmetric mating, with drift as the driver of allele-frequency change, a forward Wright-Fisher (2, 3) simulation produces X:autosome ancestry ratios in the same general range as those reported by Platt et al. (4) and Skov et al. (5). In other words, I find an enrichment of AMH X alleles in Neanderthal genomes and a desert of Neanderthal alleles in AMH X. This does not mean that sex-biased mating did not take place, but does confirm that the observed ratios are not unique signatures of sex-biased mating.

For the Neanderthal-side analysis, I modeled AMH ancestry using weighted tract-like blocks as described by Platt et al. evolving neutrally in a declining Neanderthal population (code is in supplementary material). The final statistic was measured on a sampled female Neanderthal genome as the X:autosome ratio, matching the genome-level logic of Platt et al. (6). Under a simple extreme sex-bias model in which admixture occurs only through Neanderthal males and AMH females, the expected AMH ancestry proportion on the Neanderthal X chromosome is $4/3$ as compared to the autosomes, that is, 33.3% higher on the X over the autosomes. But real finite populations do not sit exactly at their expectation. Because drift adds stochastic variance, the realized X:autosome ratio can deviate from $4/3$, so observed values above that benchmark are not, by themselves, decisive evidence against a drift-based null (Fig. 1).

For the AMH-side analysis, Neanderthal ancestry was modeled under a realistic out-of-Africa demographic trajectory with a bottleneck and subsequent expansion. The X chromosome was assigned the standard smaller effective population size relative to autosomes, that is $N_e X$ is $3/4$ ths of

the autosomes. The question was whether the observed AMH X-chromosome depletion would fall within a drift-only null before invoking mating asymmetry (Fig. 2).

First, the three Neanderthal genomes do not constitute three independent replications of the proposed mating bias. Platt et al. devote a supplementary figure (Fig. S1) to the Chagyrskaya and Vindija X:autosome ratios, presenting convergence across all three genomes as corroborating evidence. The AMH introgression event underlying the signal occurred approximately 250,000 years ago (7, 8), predating the divergence of the Altai lineage from the Chagyrskaya–Vindija lineage. All three genomes therefore inherited their X-enriched AMH ancestry from a single shared ancestral event; they are not independent observations of a mating pattern but three descendent traces of the same history. The effective sample size for the Neanderthal-side observation is closer to one, not three.

Second, the Neanderthal-side signal reported by Platt et al. is compatible with a symmetric-mating null. In the drift simulations shown in Fig. 1, 22.8% of replicates equal or exceed the reported Altai X:autosome AMH-ancestry ratio of 1.62. Thus, even under equal mating, drift alone generates values of the magnitude emphasized as evidence for sex-biased mating. Platt et al. note that drift does not alter the expectation of allele frequencies (their ref. 28, 29), which is correct — but with only 16 X-chromosome windows and a declining population, the variance around that expectation is large enough that the observed value falls well within the neutral distribution.

Third, the depletion of Neanderthal alleles on the AMH X chromosome can also arise under drift alone given the early bottlenecks and smaller effective population size of the X chromosome. The point is not that drift is proved to be the only explanation, but that the observed depletion is not outside the neutral demographic null. Fig. 2 therefore addresses the same identifiability problem from the AMH side: the observed ratio does not, by itself, require asymmetric mating.

Sex-biased mating between Neanderthals and modern humans remains a plausible hypothesis. However, because all three Neanderthal genomes trace their AMH X ancestry to a single shared introgression event, the Neanderthal-side observation is $n = 1$, not $n = 3$. Given $n = 1$, drift under symmetric mating reproduces the observed AMH enrichment on the Neanderthal X in 22.8% of simulations. Given the small effective population sizes during the AMH out-of-Africa bottleneck, drift alone also reproduces the depletion of Neanderthal alleles on the AMH X.

Fig. 1. Symmetric-mating drift null for Neanderthal X:autosome ratio

Fig. 1. Symmetric-mating drift null for Neanderthal X:autosome AMH ancestry.

Histogram of simulated X:autosome AMH-coverage ratios in sampled female Neanderthal genomes. Red line: Altai value (1.62); dashed line: 4/3 expectation under simple extreme sex bias. Under symmetric mating, 22.8% of replicates equaled or exceeded 1.62.

Fig. 2. Drift alone produces the AMH X desert under a realistic Ne trajectory
 Ne: 3,000 → 1,500 (bottleneck) → 50,000 | s = 0 (no selection) | 2000 replicates

Fig. 2. Drift-only AMH bottleneck null.

Histogram of simulated X:autosome Neanderthal ancestry ratios in AMHs under a neutral bottleneck-expansion model. Red line: observed AMH X:autosome ratio from Skov et al. (~0.6). The observed value falls within the neutral null.

References

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